

1 **Holocene moisture changes in western China, Central Asia, inferred from stalagmites**

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15

16 Abstract

17 Central Asia lies at the convergence between the Mediterranean and Asian monsoon climates
18 and the westerlies interact with the monsoon to form the climate of that region and its variability.
19 The dry mean climate makes the region highly vulnerable to changes in rainfall, underscoring the
20 need to understand its controls. We present a stalagmite-based $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record from Kesang Cave in
21 western China, using MC-ICP-MS U-series dating and stable isotope analysis. Stalagmite calcite
22 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ largely documents changes in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of precipitation. $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in stalagmites was low
23 during the early and middle Holocene (10.0-3.0 ka BP), and shifted to high values between 3.0
24 and 2.0 ka BP. After 2.0 ka BP, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ fluctuates with distinct centennial-scale variations.
25 Drawing from results of simulations of a state-of-the-art atmospheric general circulation model
26 for the preindustrial period and 9 ka BP, we propose that changes in water vapor source regions,
27 along with the prevailing moist climate, contributed to the isotopic depletion of precipitation
28 during the early and middle Holocene. Multiple records from surrounding regions indicate a
29 moistened climate during the early and middle Holocene in general, further supporting our
30 interpretation on the speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$. Changes in precipitation seasonality do not appear to be
31 a viable explanation for the observed changes, nor increased penetration of monsoonal moisture
32 to the study site. Significant discrepancies exist between the Kesang Cave speleothem calcite

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34 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record and various lake records from western China. We ascribe these disparities to the
35 different strengths and weaknesses of each archive and local environmental conditions. We
36 hypothesize that the climatic regime changed during the period 3.0-2.0 ka BP and that the
37 climate was dry since then, resulting in dominant temperature control on precipitation $\delta^{18}\text{O}$. The
38 combined effect of decreased precipitation and increased temperature around 500 AD likely
39 reduced local water availability. This might have contributed to the demise of three settlements
40 at the margin of Tarim Basin, underscoring the potential impact of climate on human habitation
41 in this region.

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43 **Keywords:** Central Asia, stalagmite, oxygen isotope, moisture source, the Holocene

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45 **1. Introduction**

46

47 The continental climate in Central Asia is presently dominated by the westerlies ([Chen et al.,](#)
48 [2008](#); [Cheng et al., 2012](#)). The Central Asian atmospheric circulation patterns play an important
49 role in linking North Atlantic and Asian monsoon climates, and its desert regions contribute
50 significantly to dust loadings over East Asia ([Zhang et al., 1997](#); [Porter and An, 1995](#); [Sun et al.,](#)
51 [2012](#); [Chiang et al., 2015](#)). The generally dry climate, dwindling water resources and fragile
52 ecosystems make Central Asian communities highly vulnerable to changes in precipitation ([Qin](#)
53 [et al., 2005](#); [Narisma et al., 2007](#), [Sorg et al., 2012](#)). Thus, understanding the causes for
54 variability of the westerlies and their interplay with the Asian summer monsoon, and
55 environmental changes in Central Asia associated with global warming is vital for the
56 assessment of current and future water resource dynamics. The westerlies also play a
57 fundamental role in aerosol distribution and dust deposition in East Asia. Well-dated and highly
58 resolved palaeoclimate reconstructions from this region serve to put today's climate dynamics
59 into a long-term perspective and to improve our capability to predict future climatic and
60 hydrological processes.

61

62 Various palaeoclimate proxy studies inform our understanding of Holocene climate and
63 environmental change in Central Asia ([Han and Qu, 1992](#); [Sun et al., 1994](#); [Mischke and](#)
64 [Wünnemann, 2006](#); [Liu et al., 2008](#); [Rudaya et al., 2009](#); [Zhong et al., 2010](#); [Wang et al., 2013](#);

65 [Zhao et al., 2015](#)). Several syntheses ([Ricketts et al., 2001](#); [Herzschuh, 2006](#); [Chen et al., 2008](#);
66 [Ran and Feng, 2013](#)) have been published over the last decade, providing valuable insights into
67 Holocene moisture dynamics of this region. However, there are divergent viewpoints on
68 Holocene moisture variability and the underlying physical mechanisms. Three different
69 viewpoints stand out: [Chen et al. \(2008\)](#) proposed that westerlies-dominated arid Central Asia
70 experienced regionally synchronous and coherent moisture changes during the Holocene. They
71 argued that the moisture history of this region is out-of-phase with that in monsoonal China,
72 implying that moisture from southern monsoonal sources did not reach Central Asia. Others
73 proposed that the moisture conveyed by the westerlies is not critical to environmental changes
74 observed in Central Asia, and that the Asian monsoon contributed substantial moisture during the
75 early and mid Holocene ([Mischke and Wünnemann, 2006](#); [Rudaya et al., 2009](#); [Zhong et al.,](#)
76 [2010](#)). A study on a lake record from Ili Valley, Xinjiang, China, suggests that climatic changes
77 near Kesang Cave are generally similar to changes observed in Asian summer monsoon-
78 governed regions since the last deglaciation. Finally, [Ran and Feng \(2013\)](#) suggested, based on
79 33 Holocene moisture reconstructions from across China, that the early Holocene was generally
80 dry and that a trend towards wetter conditions started only around 8.2 ka BP, with the last ~4 ka
81 marking the Holocene Optimum in terms of moisture conditions in the Xinjiang region.

82

83 The speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record from Kesang cave ([Cheng et al., 2012](#)), reflects $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of precipitation
84 ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precip}}$) and follows prominent precessional rhythms, with low $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values during high
85 northern Hemisphere (NH) insolation periods. Low $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precip}}$ is at odds with modern-day
86 observations that show a strong influence of temperature on $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precip}}$ in this region ([Aizen et al.,](#)
87 [2006](#)). This apparent contradiction may be resolved by intrusion of monsoon-related moisture
88 from South Asia ([Cheng et al., 2012](#)) or, alternatively, by changes in the seasonal distribution of
89 precipitation ([Kutzbach et al., 2014](#)).

90

91 These contradictory interpretations beg the question of what controls the hydrological cycle and
92 moisture distribution across Central Asia. More precisely, what is the correct interpretation of
93 changes in speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ observed in Kesang Cave? To this end, we present radiometrically
94 dated speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data from Kesang Cave. Our record confirms previously reported
95 Holocene speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data ([Cheng et al. 2012](#)), but documents changes in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precip}}$ over the

96 last thousand years in greater detail. Supported by model simulations, we propose a
97 comprehensive interpretation of speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in the context of climatic changes occurring in
98 this region. Drawing on the regional archeological record over the last 2,000 years, we show that
99 a period of significant regional climate change coincided with the demise of ancient cities around
100 Tarim Basin. This finding suggests strong dependence of historic socio-economy on regional
101 precipitation dynamics.

102

103 **2. Cave site and local climate**

104

105 Kesang Cave (N42°52', E81°45', ~2,070 m a.s.l.) is located in Tekesi County, Xinjiang
106 Autonomous Region of China (Fig. 1a). The host rock is Silurian limestone of Keketiekedaban
107 group. The current cave air temperature is ~4.9°C, slightly higher than the mean annual
108 temperature of 3.1°C at the Zhaosu Meteorological Station (N43°10', E81°08', ~1900 m a.s.l.,
109 ~60 km northwest of the Kesang Cave) from 1957 to 2000. The discrepancy is most likely due to
110 a too short observation period in the cave. The mean annual meteoric precipitation at Zhaosu
111 station is 500 mm, with >80% falling between April and September. In-cave relative humidity
112 was 88.4% in October 2010 when the cave was surveyed. CO₂ concentration in the cave was
113 measured using a hand-held Vaisala carbon dioxide meter (M170-GMP70). CO₂ increased from
114 380 ppmv to 1120 ppmv from the entrance to the inner chamber, indicating relatively weak
115 ventilation in the cave. The vegetation in the wider region around the cave site is dominated by
116 alpine meadow and forest, while the hill in which the cave formed is at present covered by *Picea*
117 *obovata* forest. Orographic uplift leads to adiabatic cooling of intruding air masses and elevated
118 precipitation with altitude in the study area (Fig. 1b).

119

120 At present, the climate and environment of semiarid-arid Central Asia are dominated by the
121 westerlies (Aizen et al., 2006; Chen et al., 2008, Cheng et al., 2012). However, strong climatic
122 diversity characterizes this region, especially concerning the seasonality of precipitation. The
123 region west of the transect from Kabul to Bishkek receives most of its annual precipitation
124 during boreal winter (between October to April), while the eastern sector receives most annual
125 precipitation during summer (from May to September, Fig. 1c) (Sorg et al. 2012). The stark
126 difference in seasonal precipitation patterns between these two regions of Central Asia is largely

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129 determined by the geography, that is, the surrounding mountain chains. This, together with the
130 interplay between the southwestern branch of the Siberian anticyclone and westerly cyclonic
131 activity determines the evolution of synoptic processes (Aizen et al., 1997).

132

133 The plains of Central Asia are open year-round to cold and dry northerly and northwesterly, as
134 well as moisture-bearing westerly inflow of air masses. The Himalaya, Pamir, Hindu Kush and
135 Tian Shan mountain ranges almost completely isolate Central Asia from southerly and easterly
136 low-level moisture-bearing air masses, originating over the Indian Ocean (Schiemann et al.,
137 2008). During summer, the northerly and northwesterly airflow causes cooling and strong winds,
138 with dust storms and minimal precipitation over the vast plains. Further east, over the high
139 rugged mountain ranges, westerly-derived air masses, bearing recycled moisture, are uplifted and
140 produce orographic rainfall. In winter, the Siberian High leads to more southern tracks of
141 westerly cyclonic intrusions which occur across southern Central Asia from Iran and Afghanistan
142 (South Caspian, Murgabic and Higher-Amudarya cyclones) with large-scale inflow of warm air.
143 As a result, increased precipitation (largely as snowfall) occurs over the Central Asia plains
144 (Schiemann et al., 2008, and references therein). In addition, the west-east oriented Tian Shan
145 Mountains mark an important climatic boundary in Central Asia: arid-desert climate
146 characterizes its south (BWk climate, Peel et al. 2007), and arid-steppe climate prevails in the
147 north (BSk, Peel et al. 2007). The Tian Shan Mountains act as important physical barrier that
148 blocks cold airflow from the north in winter. Therefore, and because of high sensitivity to
149 hydroclimatic perturbations, our study area is ideal for studying the dynamics of the westerlies.
150 On the other hand, this site is relatively unaffected by changes in winter cold flow from northern
151 Siberia and Mongolia.

152

153 3. Stalagmites and analytical methods

154

155 Stalagmite samples CNKS-2, CNKS-3, CNKS-7 and CNKS-9 from Kesang Cave are used to
156 establish the Kesang $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record, with two covering the entire Holocene and two covering the
157 last 1200 years. All stalagmites were cut in halves along their growth axes and their surfaces
158 polished. Fig. 2 illustrates the stalagmites used to establish the Kesang $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record, each with the
159 positions of ^{230}Th dates. Subsamples were drilled along growth axes and dated at the Minnesota

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161 Isotope Laboratory on the inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (Thermo Fisher
162 NEPTUNE, [Cheng et al., 2013](#)). The chemical procedures used to separate the uranium and
163 thorium for ^{230}Th dating are similar to those described in [Edwards et al., 1987](#).

164
165 Further, subsamples for stable isotope analysis were collected in two ways: 1) From samples
166 CNKS-2, CNKS-3 and CNKS-9 samples were milled from the polished half of the stalagmite at
167 intervals of 100 μm (CNKS-2, CNKS-9), 75 μm (CNKS-3, 13.5-19.6 mm) and 50 μm (CNKS-3,
168 0-13.5 mm) along the growth axis using a NewWave computer-controlled micromill; 2) From
169 sample CNKS-7 a stalagmite slab with the cross section dimensions of 0.8 \times 0.5 cm was cut using
170 a diamond saw and then sampling material was scraped off perpendicularly to the growth axis at
171 a mean resolution of \sim 20 subsamples per mm. We analysed all subsamples collected through the
172 first method and every third sample from the second method. A total of 1008 oxygen isotope
173 samples were measured on an IsoPrime 100 mass spectrometer equipped with MultiPrep at the
174 Institute of Earth Environment, Chinese Academy of Sciences. The international standard
175 NBS19 and the inter-laboratory standard TTB1 were run for every 10 to 15 samples and
176 arbitrarily selected duplicate measurements were conducted every 10 to 20 samples, respectively,
177 to check for homogeneity and reproducibility. All isotope values are reported in δ notation, the
178 per mil deviation relative to the Vienna Pee Dee Belemnite (VPDB) standard ($\delta^{18}\text{O} =$
179 $[(^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O})_{\text{sample}}/(^{18}\text{O}/^{16}\text{O})_{\text{standard}} - 1] \times 1000$). The standard results show that the external precision
180 of both $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ analysis are better than 0.15‰ (2σ).

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182 4. Results

183

184 The U/Th chronology

185 A total of 37 ^{230}Th dates were obtained from the four stalagmites. The measured isotope ratios of
186 uranium and thorium, the decay constants and the calculated ages are listed in Table 1. Here, we
187 use the bulk earth value with 50% error, i.e., $4.4 \pm 2.2 \times 10^{-6}$, a value applied by [Cheng et al.](#)
188 [\(2012\)](#), for the initial thorium correction. By using the COPRA framework ([Breitenbach et al.,](#)
189 [2012](#)), we establish the chronology (depth-age models) for each stalagmite. For the stalagmite
190 CNKS-3 we allocate 2010 AD (when we collected these samples) to the top of the stalagmite,
191 within the error margins, and recalculate the chronology, which is shown as the gray line in Fig 3.

194 We tune the chronology of CNKS-2 to that of stalagmite CNKS-3 over the period from 1500-
195 2010AD, due to the large dating error at the top of CNKS-2. The resultant chronology is also
196 shown in gray line. As shown in Fig. 3, all our tuning on the chronology lies well within the
197 range constrained by the COPRA routine with the original dates.

198

199 The age models show that stalagmites CNKS-2 and CNKS-3 were deposited during the last
200 ~1200 years. The [calculated chronologies](#) of CNKS-7 and CNKS-9 indicate that these two
201 stalagmites deposited during most of the Holocene, i.e., CNKS-9 from 7.0 ka BP to present and
202 CNKS-7 from 10.0 ka BP to 1.0 ka BP. The calculated growth rates of these stalagmites vary
203 from 1.8 mm/ka to 37.8 mm/ka, with mean growth rates of 18.3 mm/ka, 18.9 mm/ka, 6.9 mm/ka
204 and 10.6 mm/ka for stalagmites CNKS-2, CNKS-3, CNKS-7 and CNKS-9 respectively. The
205 observed variability in mean growth rates implies that the growth-controlling mechanisms (e.g.
206 drip water supply, degree of drip water supersaturation, CO₂ degassing) differed for these
207 stalagmite samples.

208

209 **Test of equilibrium deposition**

210

211 Variations in stalagmite calcite $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$) could be ascribed to changes in dripwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
212 (amount weighted isotopic composition of meteoric precipitation), cave temperature (which is
213 usually dominated by surface temperature), and physical processes of kinetic loss of CO₂ and
214 possibly evaporation of water during calcite deposition. Only if calcite has been deposited under
215 (near-)isotopic equilibrium conditions can the variations in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ be used to infer past changes in
216 cave temperature and the isotopic composition of infiltrating water. Replication is an effective
217 test for the fidelity of speleothem isotope time series as palaeoclimate reconstructions ([Dorale et
218 al., 1998](#); [Wang et al., 2001](#); [Dorale and Liu, 2009](#)). While it cannot strictly be ruled out that
219 kinetic fractionation affects multiple replicating records equally (which would thus pass the
220 replication test), the likelihood of kinetic fractionation is lower in well-replicating systems. If we
221 consider differences in temporal resolution and dating uncertainties, the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ time series of
222 CNKS-7 and CNKS-9 show significant similarities during the contemporaneous growth interval
223 of 7.5-1.5 ka BP ([as shown in Fig. 5](#)), and the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ records from CNKS-2 and CNKS-3 show
224 remarkable similarities during the overlapped growth period of 1.2-0.0 ka BP ([as shown in Fig.](#)

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229 8). Our records are also similar to the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record reported by Cheng et al. (2012) (as shown in
230 Fig. 5). The replication of all these records suggests that the stalagmites were likely deposited
231 under conditions limiting isotopic disequilibrium. Moreover, the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ profiles of our four
232 stalagmites show consistent variations during the overlapping period (Fig. 4) and can be used as
233 another replication test for the isotopic equilibrium deposition. Therefore, the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ signal
234 recorded in these four stalagmites is considered primarily of climatic origin and dictated by
235 changes in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in precipitation and cave temperature without significant kinetic
236 fractionation (Hendy, 1971).

237

238 The $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ records

239

240 Micromilling resulted in a mean temporal resolution of 7.0 years, 3.3 years and 14.9 years for
241 stalagmites CNKS-2, CNKS-3 and CNKS-9 respectively, whereas ~50 years resolution has been
242 attained for stalagmite CNKS-7 by using the manual scraping method. As shown in Fig. 5, the
243 speleothem calcite $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ varied 5.5‰ between -12‰ and -6.5‰ over the last 10,000 years, with
244 generally low values during the early and middle Holocene and high values thereafter. We
245 divided the Holocene record into three intervals: 10.0–3.0 ka BP, 3.0–2.0 ka BP, and 2.0 ka BP –
246 present, respectively, according to the observed variations in speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$, including the
247 record obtained by Cheng et al. (2012):

248 i) 10.0-3.0 ka BP. $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ values oscillate around -10.4‰ with amplitude of 2.5‰, and most of
249 them are smaller than -9.7‰. Three intervals within this phase (centered around 9.15±0.8,

250 5.75±1.9 and 3.4±0.4 ka BP) are characterized by relatively depleted $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values, while two
251 others show higher $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values (8.3-7.2 and 4.3-3.8 ka BP).

252 ii) 3.0-2.0 ka BP. This interval represents a transition phase from (i) to (iii). $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ shows a clear
253 increasing trend, accompanied by three centennial-scale oscillations.

254 iii) 2.0 ka BP-present. The $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ values fluctuate around -8.3‰ with amplitude of 3.2‰ and do
255 not show a clear long-term trend. Compared with interval (i), i.e. 10.0-3.0 ka BP, the amplitude
256 of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ fluctuations in this period is much larger, that is, 3.2‰ versus 2.5‰, with most values
257 being >-9.7‰.

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259 5. Discussion

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265 **Interpretation of speleothem calcite $\delta^{18}\text{O}$**

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267 Under isotopic equilibrium conditions, the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of speleothem calcite is a function of the cave
268 temperature and the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ signature of the parent dripwater (Hendy, 1971). Given that the
269 temperature-dependent fractionation between the calcite and water ($-0.23\text{‰}/^\circ\text{C}$, Kim and O'Neil,
270 1997) is relatively small and that Holocene temperature is estimated to have been higher by only
271 about $2.5\text{--}3.0^\circ\text{C}$ between 10-8.0 kyrs BP relative to modern values, and then decreased gradually
272 $1.5\text{--}2.0^\circ\text{C}$ since 8.0 kyrs BP (Wang Shaowu et al., 2001; Fang and Hou, 2011), the largest
273 portion of the observed $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ variation ($\sim 5.5\text{‰}$) over the Holocene is most likely dominated by
274 changes in dripwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, which is constrained by the amount weighted annual precipitation
275 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ ($\delta^{18}\text{O}_p$). It is important to note that we cannot strictly exclude any influence of temperature
276 on $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$, because higher temperature during the early-mid Holocene might have lowered $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$,
277 while lower late Holocene temperature might have increased $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$, thus increasing the total
278 amplitude of the Holocene $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ change. We argue however that changes in $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precip}}$ related to
279 changes in source and amount of precipitation outweighed potential changes associated with
280 temperature dynamics.

281

282 Modern observations reveal a strong positive correlation between precipitation $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and air
283 temperature on seasonal to decadal timescales in Central Asia (Aizen et al., 2006; Cheng et al.
284 2012) and the northern Tibetan Plateau (Thompson et al., 1989; Thompson et al., 1997),
285 suggesting temperature as the principle governing factor controlling present-day variations in
286 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_p$. This implies that speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$, which is dictated by $\delta^{18}\text{O}_p$, largely reflects local
287 temperature changes, with elevated $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values indicating increased air temperature under
288 current climate conditions. This notion however is incompatible with changes observed in
289 speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$ from Kesang Cave, which indicate low $\delta^{18}\text{O}_p$ in the early and middle Holocene
290 (Fig. 5), relative to increased $\delta^{18}\text{O}_p$ in the late Holocene. A temperature control on $\delta^{18}\text{O}_p$ would
291 imply that summertime temperatures were lower than today (recall that Kesang Cave has a
292 summer rainy season). This interpretation would directly contradict our understanding of current
293 conditions, where summertime temperatures should increase with northern hemisphere summer
294 insolation. This disparity suggests that fundamental changes must have occurred in the

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296 relationship between $\delta^{18}\text{O}_p$ and local climate (Cheng et al., 2012) in the early and mid-Holocene.
297 Below, we explore some potential causes.

298

299 1) *Penetration of Asian summer monsoon moisture into Central Asia.*

300

301 Han and Qu (1992) proposed that during the mid-Holocene the Asian summer monsoon front
302 might have reached north of the eastern Tian Shan, mirrored in high lake levels in Barkol Lake.
303 Winkler and Wang (1993) proposed that a strong early Holocene summer monsoon reached the
304 Altai Mountains, a region far northwest of the studied cave site. Jiang et al. (2007) also
305 suggested that monsoonal rainfall may have been a significant moisture source for the Wulungu
306 lake around 6 ka BP. Lacustrine sequences from lake Issyk-Kul (Ricketts et al., 2001), Boston
307 Lake (e.g., Mischke and Wünnemann, 2006) and Hoton Nuur (Rudaya et al., 2009) indicate
308 humid conditions during the early and middle Holocene, and also linked them to the penetration
309 of the Asian monsoon deep into Eurasia. The 500 ka speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record from Kesang Cave
310 (Cheng et al. 2012) shows that $\delta^{18}\text{O}_p$ was much depleted at times of high northern hemisphere
311 summer insolation (NHSI) compared to intervals of low NHSI, a behavior closely resembling
312 speleothem records in Asian summer monsoon regions (Wang et al., 2008, Cai et al., 2015).

313

314 Analysis of modern climate in Xinjiang suggests that summertime rainfall in Xinjiang varies in
315 response to the west Asian subtropical westerly jet (WASJ). A southward shift of the WASJ is
316 favorable for warm and wet air penetrating from low southwesterly latitudes into Central Asia
317 and Xinjiang, leading to increased indirect moisture transport from the Indian Ocean and higher
318 rainfall (Zhao et al., 2014a; 2014b). Zhao et al. (2014b) further argue that increased summer
319 precipitation in Xinjiang is potentially linked with a weakened Indian summer monsoon (ISM).
320 A weakened ISM may lead to middle and upper tropospheric cooling over Central Asia which in
321 turn induces a southward shift of the WASJ over western and Central Asia. Moreover, with less
322 moisture feeding the ISM, more moisture can be diverted to Central Asia (Zhao et al., 2014b).
323 However, this specific mechanism – a southward WASJ shift from a weakened ISM, leading to
324 increased monsoonal moisture into Central Asia – appears to contradict our current
325 understanding that the ISM was stronger during the early and mid-Holocene relative to today
326 (Fleitmann et al., 2007; Cai et al., 2012). The mechanism proposed by Zhao and coworkers

327 (2014b) is based on analysis of modern-day inter-annual variability, which might not be an
328 adequate analogue for early to mid-Holocene climate conditions. Moreover, early and middle
329 Holocene circulation patterns might have significantly differed from today's. Thus, it appears
330 unlikely that the penetration of South Asian moisture explains the depletion of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precip}}$ and
331 wetter climate during the early and middle Holocene in Central Asia.

332

333 2) *Changes to precipitation seasonality.*

334

335 Winter precipitation, which in Xinjiang occurs largely as snow, is characterized by very low
336 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_p$. Thus, an increase in the fraction of winter precipitation would lower the amount-weighted
337 annual $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precip}}$ signature. Kesang Cave is potentially very sensitive to seasonal changes as it is
338 located close to the boundary between summer precipitation dominance and winter precipitation
339 dominance as one moves from east to west (Fig. 1c). A relatively small eastward shift of this
340 seasonality boundary would change precipitation seasonality at Kesang Cave, shifting it from a
341 summer rainfall-regime to a winter snowfall-dominated one, resulting in depleted precipitation
342 and dripwater $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values. Climate model simulations by Kutzbach et al. (2014) suggest that
343 winter precipitation is likely to increase in Central Asia during periods of maximum Northern
344 Hemisphere seasonality (summer perihelion, winter aphelion); this lends some model support to
345 the interpretation of oxygen isotope changes in the Kesang record. A strengthening of winter
346 precipitation has also been evoked to explain low $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values at other locations, such as the
347 Eastern Mediterranean during precession minima and summer insolation maxima (Bar-Matthews
348 et al., 1997; 2003; Tzedakis, 2007). However, simulations with the Community Climate System
349 Model, version 3 (CCSM3), carried out by Kutzbach et al. (2014) did not reveal any significant
350 regime shift, thus not lending model support to the above hypothesis. It is possible that the
351 rugged topography has a stronger control over the pattern of seasonal precipitation distribution in
352 this region, limiting the reaction of the regime boundary to precession-induced climatic and
353 environmental changes. Alternatively, the relatively coarse resolution (3.75° in latitude/longitude
354 grid) in their simulations may be insufficient to distinguish this minor shift and high resolution
355 regional model simulations might be needed to test this hypothesis.

356

357 3) *Changes in the isotope composition of moisture sources.*

358

359 $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precip}}$ integrates various processes in the hydrological cycle, such as water vapor source
360 dynamics influenced by evaporation and transpiration, horizontal and vertical mixing, as well as
361 phase transitions among ice, liquid, and vapor (Dansgaard, 1964, Risi et al. 2008, Breitenbach et
362 al. 2010). Central Asia receives its moisture largely from re-evaporation (that is, recycling) from
363 surrounding areas, and thus depends on locality and season of the westerlies and the ISM.
364 Comparing the synoptic climatology and meteorological data with $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and d-excess in firn
365 cores from the Tian Shan, Aizen et al. (2006) found that precipitation in Central Asia/western
366 China is mainly derived from recycled moisture from the Aral–Caspian basin (~54%), and the
367 Mediterranean and Black Seas (~33%), with only a small fraction (~13%) originating from the
368 North Atlantic realm. This finding suggests that changes in the isotopic composition of these
369 western basins may influence $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precip}}$ in Central Asia.

370

371 ~~All~~ speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ data from the eastern Mediterranean, the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record derived from *G. ruber*
372 from the Eastern Mediterranean Sea and the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record of lake aragonite from Dead Sea Basin
373 indicate that $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in precipitation decreased during high northern hemisphere summer insolation
374 periods, whereas precipitation amount increased (occurred in winter, Bar-Matthews et al., 1997;
375 2003; Kolodny et al., 2005; Almogi-Labin et al., 2009; Torfstein et al., 2009; Cheng et al., 2015),
376 reflecting intensified winter storm tracks (Kutzbach et al., 2014). Stronger westerlies would have
377 carried moisture from more westerly sources, resulting in lower surface water $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in the re-
378 evaporation regions feeding Kesang Cave during these intervals. Such change should be
379 reflected in a shift to a wintertime precipitation regime. Simultaneously, an intensified Indian
380 summer monsoon would lead to depleted $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precip}}$ in the southern Tibetan Plateau (Cai et al.,
381 2010, 2012), potentially complicating the interpretation of speleothem-based $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ by adding ^{18}O -
382 depleted moisture during summer.

383

384 It is thus likely that the depletion of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precip}}$ at our study site during high NHSI reflects changes
385 in water vapor $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ from its source regions. Furthermore, generally wetter climate conditions
386 may lead to higher relative humidity around the cave site, reducing re-evaporation of raindrops
387 and isotopic enrichment of $\delta^{18}\text{O}_{\text{precip}}$ during rain events, as demonstrated in northern China (Lee
388 and Fung, 2008; 2012).

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393 To explore this further, we analyze two simulations for the preindustrial period (0 ka) and 9 ka
394 BP, using the Community Atmosphere Model 5 (CAM5, Hurrell et al., 2013) at the standard
395 $0.9^\circ \times 1.25^\circ$ resolution, and coupled to a slab ocean. We used standard CMIP5 preindustrial
396 boundary conditions, and the 9 ka BP simulation differs from the 0 ka simulation only in that the
397 calendar date was set to -7000 AD, and methane level set to 650 ppb; ice sheet boundary
398 conditions were kept constant. Both simulations were performed as part of a study of the
399 Holocene East Asian summer monsoon and we refer the reader to Kong et al. (2016) for details
400 of the model simulations.

401

402 The preindustrial CAM5 simulation resembles today's summer-dominated precipitation
403 seasonality at the grid point closest to Kesang Cave (81.75°E , 42.9°N , Fig. 6b), as well as the
404 boundary in precipitation seasonality over Central Asia, between the winter-dominated west and
405 the summer-dominated east (Fig. 6a). The transition is located at ca. 73°E , in agreement with
406 observed patterns. The simulations also show that early spring rainfall near Kesang Cave is
407 dominated by large-scale precipitation presumably from orographic uplift, whereas later in the
408 spring and summer precipitation becomes convective in nature (not shown). The 9 ka simulation
409 indicates that precipitation seasonality remains intact across the region, with the western segment
410 remaining winter-, and the eastern segment summer-dominated. However, rainfall seasonality in
411 the summer-dominated eastern region shows a shift of the rainfall season to a slightly later date.
412 Over the Kesang grid point, rainfall is reduced in April (mostly due to reduced large-scale
413 precipitation) and increased during the peak summer months (due to increased convective
414 precipitation) in the Holocene thermal maximum simulation (Fig. 6b).

415 Thus, these simulations seem to eliminate changes in precipitation seasonality (point 2 above) as
416 a viable explanation for the observed early Holocene Kesang $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ pattern. The model results
417 suggest that topography exerts the dominant control on precipitation seasonality in this region.

418

419 Decreased April rains in the 9 ka simulation can be explained by a colder and drier atmosphere
420 upwind of Kesang over western Central Asia, forced by prevailing northerly low-level winds
421 (note that winter NH insolation is lower at 9 ka BP). On the other hand, peak summer months
422 were wetter because higher NH summer insolation led to widespread warming of the entire

423 Central Asian/Tibetan Plateau region, with corresponding increased convection over Kesang
424 Cave (Fig. 7a). Atmospheric moistening over Kesang Cave appears to have been embedded in a
425 wider pattern that affected the entire region, suggesting intensified monsoonal influence on
426 moisture availability. Moreover, the prevailing zonal moisture transport to Kesang increased by
427 ca. 20% and meridional transport by ca. 40%, broadly consistent with the modeled moister
428 atmosphere (not shown). These findings suggest that increased penetration of monsoonal
429 moisture deep into the Tarim basin region (point 1 above) is a potentially viable explanation for
430 the dynamics in the speleothem record. However, if we take the simulations simply at face value
431 - that neither amount nor seasonality of precipitation over Kesang changed fundamentally - it is
432 difficult to argue for an increased penetration of monsoonal moisture to explain the speleothem
433 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record with its large change of 5.5‰.

434
435 Given that the simulations appear to eliminate both scenarios (1) and (2) above, we are left with
436 changes in the isotopic composition of the source moisture as the potential remaining
437 explanation. Indeed, a recent study by Battisti et al. (2014) appears to support this mechanism:
438 their isotope-enabled simulations indicate significant shifts to lower June-August precipitation-
439 weighed $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ over northeastern Africa and the Arabian Peninsula (by ~4-5 ‰), Persia (by ~2-3
440 ‰), and the Tibetan Plateau (by ~4-7 ‰) from a low NH insolation forcing (207 ka BP) to a
441 high NH insolation forcing (218 ka BP) [see figure 8b of Battisti et al. 2014]. The authors argue
442 that the main reason for this change is a corresponding depletion in the imported water vapor into
443 these regions. Whether such depletion of the source moisture is due to changes in source water
444 composition, temperature, humidity, or changes in Rayleigh processes along the transport
445 pathway remains to be studied in greater detail.

446
447 What does this imply for the Kesang Cave record? We note that Battisti et al. (2014) did not find
448 isotopic changes in their simulations that would match the orbital signal at Kesang Cave,
449 possibly due to the relatively coarse model resolution. The authors also point to other potential
450 model shortcomings, including incorrect storm track position and model errors in fractionation at
451 low temperatures. That being said, summertime moisture over Kesang Cave remained primarily
452 derived from re-evaporation upstream: according to the 9 ka simulation, the majority of the
453 moisture came directly from westerly sources, including the Aral-Caspian basin, the

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454 Mediterranean and the Black Sea (Fig. 7b), where surface water was depleted in the early and
455 middle Holocene (e.g., Bar-Matthews et al., 1997; 2003; Kolodny et al., 2005; Almogi-Labin et
456 al., 2009; Torfstein et al., 2009; Cheng et al., 2015). An appreciable fraction of precipitation over
457 Kesang Cave is also derived from re-evaporation over the Tibetan Plateau to the south, where
458 lighter $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ has been found in both speleothems (Cai et al., 2012) and models (Battisti et al.
459 2014) (Fig. 7c). Moisture that was strongly depleted at the original source and subsequently
460 recycled and transported to Kesang Cave during summer has the potential to retain the observed
461 depleted early-mid Holocene $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values, as long as the depletion in ^{18}O at the first moisture
462 source exceeds the enrichment during recycling. Reconstructions from Peqin Cave, Northern
463 Israel (Bar-Matthews et al. 2003) and Jeita Cave, Lebanon (Cheng et al., 2015) show that the
464 precipitation in the Eastern Mediterranean was depleted in ^{18}O during the period from ~10.0 ka
465 BP to ~7.5 ka BP and subsequently enriched gradually to ~4.5 ka BP, while $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in the Asian
466 monsoon realm (Dongge Cave, Southern China, Wang et al., 2005) increased gradually since
467 ~7.0 ka BP to ~2.0 ka BP (Fig. 5). The long-term increasing trend likely indicate the regional
468 responses of Mediterranean and Asian summer monsoon climates to insolation changes during
469 the Holocene. The difference in timing of these changes suggests the divergence of regional
470 climate system responding to the global climate change. In general, the Kesang $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record
471 shows much similarity to these two records from west and east during the early period of ~10.0 -
472 ~4.3 ka BP, but differs significantly after 4.0 ka BP for about 1300 years. We hypothesize that
473 this depletion might be partly caused by increased contribution/fraction of moisture supply from
474 surrounding glaciers, as glacier ice was much depleted in ^{18}O . Definite resolution of this issue
475 will require high-resolution simulations with isotope-enabled climate models.

476
477 During the last 2000 years, temperature is likely a major factor influencing $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in precipitation
478 at our cave site, as demonstrated by modern observations (Aizen et al., 2006). However,
479 temperature dependent fractionation of 0.55‰ per degree at mid latitudes (Dansgaard, 1964)
480 cannot account for the large amplitude of 3.5‰, because temperature dependent fractionation
481 between calcite and dripwater is negatively correlated with temperature (ca. -0.23‰/°C, Kim and
482 O'Neil, 1997), and cancels ca. half of the temperature impact on the precipitation $\delta^{18}\text{O}$. Below-
483 cloud evaporation during precipitation may amplify the temperature effect as high temperature
484 may accelerate evaporation substantially (Lee et al. 2012), leading to increased temperature

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- Comment [Office1]: I am not sure about this. How would glacier meltwater contribute? Is that recycled moisture? Or do you mean direct infiltration into the cave? I rather believe that the regional climate went through a tipping point, where the moisture source became less important and the temperature effect overwhelmed the d18O signal... could that be a viable explanation?
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510 dependent fractionation (e.g. 0.75‰/°C at Hetian, [Johnson and Ingram, 2004](#)). Evaporation
511 before infiltration into the epikarst system could further elevate $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of soil- and dripwater. All
512 these factors act in the same direction and would amplify the temperature effects on dripwater
513 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and thus speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$. In this complex pattern speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ likely reflects
514 temperature during the last ~2000 years, with high $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ signifying elevated temperature and vice
515 versa. This explanation invokes a shift from a strong moisture composition influence, to a
516 temperature forcing on $\delta^{18}\text{O}_c$.

517

518 **Holocene climate change recorded in Kesang Cave and comparison with other proxy** 519 **records**

520

521 Above we argued that low speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values observed in the Kesang record indicate
522 moister climate conditions during the early and mid Holocene (10-3 ka BP), while since ca. 2 ka
523 BP generally high $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values might reflect regional temperature variability. This inference is
524 corroborated by the fact that over the last 500 ka most interglacial speleothem growth intervals in
525 Kesang Cave began with low $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values ([Cheng et al., 2012](#)). Lake sediments from the nearby
526 sites largely indicate a relatively wet early and middle Holocene. For example, multi-proxy
527 records from lake Issyk-Kul suggest a wet early Holocene, followed by more arid conditions
528 ([Ricketts et al., 2001](#); [Rasmussen et al., 2001](#)). Pollen deposition rates and the *Artemisia* to
529 *Chenopodiaceae* ratio from Manas Lake indicate desert steppe vegetation between 10.5 ka BP to
530 9.0 ka BP, and after 4.2 ka BP, whereas steppe vegetation developed in the intervening period,
531 implying relatively humid conditions in the early and mid Holocene ([Sun et al., 1994](#)). Boston
532 lake, located east of the cave site, documented rising lake levels starting ~8.2 ka BP and reaching
533 a maximum ~7.0 kyr BP, with subsequent gradually decline ([Wünnemann et al., 2006](#); [Huang et al., 2009](#)).
534 In particular, the sedimentary profile from Yili Valley, close to Kesang Cave, shows
535 lacustrine sediments for the early and mid Holocene, but loess deposits since ~3 ka BP, again
536 indicating a shift to drier conditions at ~3 ka BP ([Li et al., 2011](#)). The pollen record extracted
537 from this profile also revealed two fluctuations between humid and relatively dry conditions
538 during the early and mid Holocene, following a pattern similar to our $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record, considering
539 the chronological uncertainties.

540

541 Our inference differs to some degree from the regional synthesis by Chen et al. (2008) and is
542 largely opposite to the synthesis by Ran and Feng (2013). Inconsistencies between speleothem
543 and lake sediments can potentially be attributed to that the different proxies used may not record
544 the same aspects of the hydrological cycle in this region. Changes in lake levels and pollen
545 assemblages used in these studies are mainly indicative of variations of effective moisture, which
546 contains a signal of evaporative loss but not amount of rainfall alone. Additionally, local
547 geomorphological configurations may impact meltwater supply to these lakes, potentially
548 resulting in differences in apparent water supply, since meltwater plays a major role in
549 influencing lake levels in this region (Kaser et al., 2010).

550
551 Furthermore the two syntheses cover different regions. Chen et al. (2008) used sediment cores
552 from a vast region extending from 43.20°E to 117.38°E in arid Central Asia, while Ran and Feng
553 (2013) used only sediment cores from northwestern China (from 81.20°E to 94.2°E). Although
554 an average moisture index is good at producing a regionally representative picture, it smoothens
555 details characteristic to individual sites. Prerequisite for a regional average is that all proxy
556 indices record the same aspect of climate and that reconstructions for a particular region
557 demonstrate a geographically coherent trend. Fig. 1C shows that precipitation seasonality
558 changes from west to east, implying that atmospheric circulation and precipitation dynamics
559 differ in these two regions (Sorg et al. 2012). It might therefore be unfavorable to directly
560 compare and average the different records from western and eastern Central Asia. It thus is
561 unrealistic to interpret all these records between the eastern Mediterranean region and western
562 China using a single mechanism.

563
564 However, generally moister conditions in western Central Asia (with dominant winter
565 precipitation) and eastern Central Asia (with dominant summer precipitation) (Bar-Matthews et
566 al., 2003; Herzschuh, 2006; Chen et al., 2008; Li et al., 2011; Cheng et al., 2012) seems robustly
567 established for the early and mid-Holocene. Wetter conditions in both regions might be caused
568 by precession-related forcing of seasonal NH insolation changes, as suggested by Kutzbach et al.
569 (2014). Increased precipitation in western Central Asia was likely caused by enhanced
570 wintertime westerly storm tracks (Kutzbach et al., 2014), whereas increased humidity, higher
571 rainfall and reduced evaporation in summer in eastern Central Asia might be linked to intensified

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572 moisture transport from the Aral–Caspian basin, Mediterranean Sea and North Atlantic (Chen et
573 al., 2008), and possibly from regions affected by the Asian summer monsoon (Cheng et al.,
574 2012).

575

576 From ~3-2 ka BP, stalagmite $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ increases to a mean $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ value about 2.0 permil higher than in
577 the early and mid-Holocene. This prominent shift suggests that the region's climate changed
578 from a relatively humid regime to noticeably drier conditions. Late Holocene conditions
579 facilitated enhanced evaporation from the surrounding basins, progressively reducing moisture
580 availability (Cheng et al., 2012), and eventually engendering domination of temperature effects
581 on $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in precipitation.

582

583 Over the last 2000 years, the Kesang $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ records are characterized by distinct centennial-scale
584 variations (Fig. 5 and Fig. 8), whereas multi-decadal and even shorter timescales are insignificant
585 (Fig. 8). This suggests that centennial-scale variations may play a leading role in temperature
586 fluctuations in western China and Central Asia, although water storage in the aquifer and thermal
587 insulation of the host rock probably buffer temperature changes to a certain degree. Following
588 the interpretation outlined above three cold periods can be identified, i.e. 800-900 AD, 1200-
589 1300 AD, and 1570-1680 AD (gray bars in Fig. 8), with the last being synchronous with the
590 Little Ice Age. Several warm phases interrupt these cold periods, with a prominent warming
591 trend at the end the record that might be related to the warming since the 1970s. As shown in Fig.
592 8, the Kesang reconstruction is in general agreement with ice-core and tree-ring based
593 temperature reconstructions from the central-eastern Tibetan Plateau (Yao et al., 1996; Liu et al,
594 2009), which have been correlated with temperature changes in western China (Liu et al., 2013).

595 During the cold period from 800-900 AD, the Kesang record differs from the palaeoclimate
596 reconstructions in the central-eastern Tibetan Plateau. Lower coverage by tree-ring data and
597 larger uncertainties (Liu et al, 2009) may cause this lack of correspondence during this period.

598

599 For the last 1200 years, the Kesang speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ time series shows much similarity to the
600 Guliya ice core $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record (Yao et al., 1996) and is consistent with the temperature record from
601 the southern Inylchek Glacier from Kyrgyzstan (Aizen 2008, Fig. 8), considering the
602 chronological uncertainty of the speleothem record in the last century. This indicates that the

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605 larger region of western China, including the Guliya and our cave sites might have experienced
606 similar climatic changes and that snow accumulation at Guliya might be used to infer the
607 moisture history in western China.

608

609 The last 1700 years of snow accumulation recorded in the Guliya ice core reveal a significant
610 decrease in precipitation from 400-600 AD. At the same time, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in the ice core was enriched
611 for ca. 100 years, indicating a warm and/or dry period around 600 AD. Increased precipitation
612 (indicated by higher snow accumulation rates) and [relatively low temperature intervals](#) reflected
613 in speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}_\text{c}$ and in the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ of Guliya ice core during the Little Ice Age suggest [a high](#)
614 [potential of](#) wetter climate, which has also been documented in the sediments from Lop Nur ([Liu](#)
615 [et al., 2013](#)) and [geo-biological records from Tarim Basin \(Putnam et al., 2016\)](#).

616

617 **Impact of climate change on human society in Central Asia over the last 2,000 years**

618

619 The role of climatic and environmental changes in determining the success and failure of
620 societies is still intensely debated ([deMenocal, 2001](#); [Yancheva et al., 2007](#); [Zhang et al., 2005](#);
621 [Zhang et al., 2010](#), [Donges et al. 2015](#)). Ascribing all episodes of societal change to climatic
622 events would be too simplistic in Asia, where advanced and complex dynastic societies existed
623 in various climatic and eco-zones ([Zhang et al., 2010](#), [Cunliffe 2015](#)). In arid western China and
624 Central Asia, water availability rather than temperature, is the prime climatic determinant for
625 complex human societies. Shifts in moisture distribution across this region likely had significant
626 impacts on ancient civilizations ([Cunliffe 2015](#)), which likely mitigated climatic changes by
627 gradually reorganizing systems of supply and production, or abandoning of urban centers (under
628 unfavorable conditions), etc. Placing the archaeological record of cultural change within the
629 context of detailed and well-dated palaeoclimate records presents opportunities to examine how
630 local societies responded to climatic changes ([deMenocal, 2001](#); [Donges et al. 2015](#)).

631

632 Early indications of Neolithic settlements are found in the lower reaches of the Tarim River, and
633 a ^{14}C age of 3800 years BP has been reported from an archaeological site at Tomb Valley in this
634 region ([Wang, 1996](#)). Wheat grains, found in the tomb suggest early agricultural activity in
635 Tarim region, likely associated with a moist climate at that time.

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638 The famous ancient city of Loulan, located on the western bank of Lake Lop Nor in the
639 northeastern Tarim Basin, was once the political, economic and cultural center of western China
640 from c. 77 BC to AD 550 (Ban, 92; Xia et al., 2007). Historical documents as well as grains of
641 common millet, naked barley and wheat suggest active agriculture at the time (Wang, 1983).
642 Large-scale reclamation of wasteland around Loulan occurred in the eastern Han dynasty (Fan,
643 444). Active agricultural practice and a flourishing economy were also documented at the two
644 relic sites of Niya and Keria Oasis as early as ~400 AD (Wang et al, 1998). All these lines of
645 evidence suggest a relatively wet climate and sufficient water resources to support societal
646 development.

647

648 However, this once prosperous city succumbed to desertification and the region was depopulated
649 when the Buddhist monk Xuanzang passed through the area in about 645 AD during the Tang
650 dynasty (Xuanzang, 645). ¹⁴C ages of reed remains and wood material found in the ruins, as well
651 as the official literature and archaeological relics suggest that these settlements were populated
652 until ~400 AD, and then gradually fell victim to abandonment till about 600 AD (Wang, 1998).
653 Palaeobotanical evidence obtained from Loulan and Milan also suggests that the landscape of
654 ancient Loulan was a typical oasis before desertification and abandonment (Zhang et al., 2013).

655

656 The synchronicity between abandonment around 400 AD and a climate shift to drier conditions
657 (Fig. 8) suggests a significant influence of climate on human habitation, likely due to shortage of
658 sustainable water resources as the root cause (Wang, 1998). Higher temperature and decreased
659 precipitation may have aggravated regional aridity which eventually lead to the abandonment of
660 these settlements at the margin of Tarim Basin.

661

662 Unfortunately, currently available archaeological data is too sparse and climate reconstructions
663 need further improvements to draw more specific conclusions about possible links between
664 climatic perturbations and changes in societies in western China. Further studies on human
665 activities in this region are warranted.

666

667 **6. Conclusions**

668
669 A U-series dated high-resolution isotope reconstruction based on multiple stalagmites from
670 Kesang Cave is used to establish a Holocene $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ time series for western China, Central Asia.
671 Our record indicates low precipitation $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ during the early and middle Holocene, i.e., from
672 10.0-3.0 ka BP, increased precipitation $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ from 3.0 to 2.0 ka BP, and high values with distinct
673 centennial-scale variations after 2.0 ka BP. For the early and mid Holocene, stalagmite calcite
674 $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ largely documents changes in precipitation $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, whereas temperature is likely the
675 dominant factor controlling the speleothem $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and possibly amplified by the dry climate after
676 ca. 2 ka BP.

677 Three potential mechanisms could explain the depletion of precipitation $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ during the early
678 and middle Holocene: (i) the penetration of monsoon-related moisture put forward by Cheng et
679 al., 2012; (ii) changes in precipitation seasonality suggested by Kutzbach et al., 2014; and (iii)
680 changes in the isotopic composition of moisture sources proposed in this study. CAM5 model
681 simulations for the preindustrial period and 9 ka BP appear to rule out changes in precipitation
682 seasonality as a viable explanation. The model results further challenge the hypothesis of
683 increased penetration of monsoonal moisture, as simulated moisture transport is essentially
684 unchanged in the 9 ka BP simulation.

- 685 • We propose that changes in the isotopic composition of moisture coming from
686 surrounding source regions, along with a moistened climate may have contributed to the
687 depletion of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ in precipitation during the early and middle Holocene. Available
688 records from surrounding regions and also the Ili Basin (the cave site) also suggest a
689 general moistened climate during the early and middle Holocene and corroborate our
690 interpretation.
- 691 • Our data reveal that the regional climatic regime changed ca. 3.0-2.0 ka BP, with
692 temperature dominating precipitation $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and a dry climate since then. The inferred
693 temperature changes at the cave site generally agree with the Guliya ice core and a tree
694 ring-based temperature reconstruction from the Middle Eastern Tibetan Plateau,
695 confirming the large spatial scale temperature change in western China over the last 2000
696 years.
- 697 • During the last 2000 years, temperature changes reveal strong centennial-scale
698 oscillations. The combined effects of decreased precipitation and increased temperature

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713 around 500 AD reduced local water availability and likely contributed to the demise of
714 three settlements at the margin of Tarim Basin, substantiating that the climate changes
715 profoundly affected human society in this area. Detailed comparisons of palaeoclimate
716 and archaeological data are needed to unravel the complexities of human adaptation and
717 response to environmental dynamics.
718

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997 Captions

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999 Figure 1. a) Location of different records in topographic map. GTOPO30 data distributed by
1000 U.S. Geological Survey's EROS (Earth Resources Observation and Science;
1001 http://eros.usgs.gov/#/Find_Data/Products_and_Data_Available/gtopo30_info) Data Center were
1002 used to plot topographic map. Averaged wind field at 850 hPa isobaric in summer (white arrow)
1003 and winter (red arrow) from 1981 to 2010 (NCEP Reanalysis Derived data provided by the
1004 NOAA/OAR/ESRL PSD, Boulder, Colorado, USA, from their Web site at
1005 <http://www.esrl.noaa.gov/psd/>). b) Mean annual precipitation (mm) in the study region from
1006 1951 to 2007. The scale indicates the power of 10. c) The mean ratio of the winter half year
1007 (January to April, November and December) precipitation to annual precipitation in the study
1008 region from 1951 to 2007. Precipitation seasonality shifts from west (dominated by winter
1009 precipitation) to east (dominated by summer precipitation). The location of Kesang Cave (as well
1010 as the Yili Basin) is denoted by red star (N42°52', E81°45', ~2070m a.b.s.l.), all other records are
1011 denoted by pink circles: G, Guliya Ice core, N35°17', E81°29'; I, Issyk-Kul Lake, N42°30',
1012 E77°06'; S, Sayram Lake, N44°36', E81°12'; M, Manas Lake, N45°48', E86°00'; B, Boston
1013 Lake, N42°00', E87°01'.

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1015 Figure 2. The cross sections of stalagmites CNKS-2, CNKS-3, CNKS-7 and CNKS-9 cut along
1016 the growth axis showing bands of growth layers. ²³⁰Th dating results are also indicated beside the
1017 drilling position.

1018

1019 Figure 3. Plots of the age versus depth for stalagmite CNKS-2, CNKS-3, CNKS-7 and CNKS-9.
1020 Ages of CNKS-7 and CNKS-9 are reported as thousand years before the present (1950), ka BP,
1021 while that of CNKS-2 and CNKS-3 are reported as calendar year (year /AD). The age errors
1022 indicated in the plots are 2σ error. COPRA, a depth-age modeling program (Breitenbach et al.,
1023 2012), is used to calculate the chronologies of all these stalagmites. The red line indicates the
1024 confidence level of 95%. In panels of CNKS-2 and CNKS-3, the gray lines show the tuned
1025 chronology we used in the following plots (see the text for details), and the black line show the
1026 COPRA output calculated with U-series dates.

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1031 Figure 4. The time series of speleothem $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ obtained from Kesang Cave. The red and blue
1032 colors denote different stalagmites in each panel. Replications in $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ during the overlapped
1033 periods further confirm these stalagmites are most likely deposited under the isotopic equilibrium
1034 conditions and that the variations of $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ are dominated by climate variations, i.e., changes in
1035 the oxygen isotopic composition of meteoric precipitation and cave temperature at the time of
1036 calcite precipitation.

1037

1038 Figure 5. (A) Comparison of oxygen isotopic records from stalagmites CNKS-7 (red), CNKS-9
1039 (blue) and those reported in Cheng et al. (2012) from Kesang Cave (dark gray) with the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
1040 records from Dongge Cave (dark green, Wang et al., 2005), southern China, Peqiin Cave,
1041 northern Israel (violet, Bar-Matthews, 2003, GCA) and Jeita Cave, Lebanon (light green, Cheng
1042 et al., 2015). The horizontal pink lines above the Kesang time series indicate the mean $\delta^{18}\text{O}$
1043 values of -10.4‰ and -8.3‰ during the periods of 10.7-3.0 ka BP (light green shaded) and after
1044 2.0 ka BP (light yellow shaded), respectively. The dashed line indicates the value of -9.7‰,
1045 which demarcates the shift from mainly lower than most $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values in the early period (10.7-
1046 3.0 ka BP) to higher values the later period (after 2.0 ka BP) (B) Reconstructed moisture changes
1047 at different sites in central Asia based on lake sediments, i.e., Lake Issyk-Kul, Ricketts et al.
1048 2001; Yili Basin, Li et al., 2011; Sayram Lake, Jiang et al., 2013; Manas Lake, Sun et al., 1994;
1049 Boston Lake, Wünnemann et al., 2006. The different gray-shaded bars indicate reconstructed
1050 climatic conditions, i.e., from black to light gray illustrating wetter to relatively drier conditions.

1051

1052 Figure 6. (a) Hovmoller diagram of precipitation seasonality over central Asian as simulated in
1053 the CAM5 preindustrial simulation. It shows rainfall (contour interval 0.5mm/d) of
1054 climatological rainfall at 42.9°N, which is the latitude of Kesang Cave. The wintertime-
1055 dominated precipitation seasonality is clearly seen to the west of ~73°E, and the summertime-
1056 dominated seasonality to the east of ~73°E. The dashed line is the approximate longitude of
1057 Kesang Cave. (b) Monthly mean rainfall climatology at the gridpoint closest to Kesang Cave
1058 (81.75°E, 42.9°N) for the preindustrial simulation (solid line) and the 9ka simulation (dashed

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- Deleted: The gray bars indicate the reconstructed climatic conditions, i.e., from black to light gray illustrating the climate from relatively wet to relatively dry.
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- Moved up [1]: The gray bars indicate the reconstructed climatic conditions, i.e., from black to light gray illustrating the climate from relatively wet to relatively dry. The yellow and green lines in Kesang plot indicate the mean $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ values during the periods of 10.7-3.0 ka BP (light green shaded) and after 2.0 ka BP (light yellow shaded), respectively.
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1089 line). 9ka rainfall (mm/d) is slightly weaker during the spring, and slightly increased in the
1090 summer, compared to the preindustrial.

1091

1092 Figure 7. (a) Difference in the June-August specific humidity over the Tibetan Plateau and Tarim
1093 basin, 9ka minus preindustrial. The data is averaged over 80°E-83°E, encompassing the
1094 longitude of Kesang Cave. Contour interval 0.2 g/kg. (b) Zonal moisture transport (UQ) for the
1095 9ka simulation averaged over 41°N to 44°N, encompassing the Kesang latitude. (c) Meridional
1096 moisture transport (VQ) for the 9ka simulation averaged over 40°N to 42°N, just south of
1097 Kesang Cave. For (b) and (c), the contour interval is 5(m/s)(g/kg) and positive values imply
1098 eastward or northward transport. In all panels, the black dashed line indicates the approximate
1099 location of Kesang Cave.

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1101 Figure 8. Comparisons of the Kesang stalagmite $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ records (red, CNKS-3; blue, CNKS-2;
1102 gray, CNKS-9) with the $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ (brown) and accumulation (purple) records of Guliya Ice core (Yao
1103 et al., 1996), and the tree ring record from the central-eastern Tibetan Plateau (Liu et al, 2009).
1104 The ice core reconstructed temperature changes (green) at the Tien Shan southern Inylchek
1105 Glacier, Kyrgyzstan (Aizen, 2008), were also present along with the Guliya ice core $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record.
1106 The two cyan lines are also the Kesang $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ records of CNKS-2 and CNKS-3.

1107

Table 1. ²³⁰Th dating results. The error is 2σ error.

Sample Number	Distance from top/mm	²³⁸ U (ppb)	²³² Th (ppt)	²³⁰ Th / ²³² Th (atomic x10 ⁶)	δ ²³⁴ U* (measured)	²³⁰ Th / ²³⁸ U (activity)	²³⁰ Th Age (yr) (uncorrected)	²³⁰ Th Age (yr BP)*** (corrected)	δ ²³⁴ U _{initial} ** (corrected)
CNKS-2-19	1.9	674.4±1.9	11702±33	9.5±0.5	1024.0±5.3	0.0100±0.0005	542±29	235±128	1024.9±5.3
CNKS-2-53	5.3	727.2±1.1	1733±35	88.8±2.5	1000.7±3.1	0.0128±0.0003	702±14	605±28	1002.6±3.2
CNKS-2-81	8.1	703.3±2.1	2377±7	80.1±1.5	998.5±5.6	0.0164±0.0003	899±17	792±30	1000.9±5.6
CNKS-2-119	11.9	741.7±1.0	10641±213	25.0±0.6	990.9±2.5	0.0217±0.0002	1196±13	924±149	993.6±2.6
CNKS-2-149	14.9	651.7±2.3	13615±58	21.4±1.0	1045.9±6.8	0.0271±0.0013	1454±71	1098±165	1049.3±6.8
CNKS-3-5	0.5	663.9±0.9	10281± 206	8.3±0.3	1069.1± 2.8	0.0078±0.0002	410±13	130±155	1069.7±2.8
CNKS-3-30	3	701.9±1.8	4402±11	20.7±0.7	1009.1±4.7	0.0079±0.0003	428±16	279±48	1010.1±4.7
CNKS-3-56	5.6	749.5±1.0	4043±81	31.1±1.0	968.0±2.7	0.0102±0.0002	566±14	424±58	969.3±2.7
CNKS-3-90	9	636.0±0.8	1864±38	84.0±2.4	1043.7±2.9	0.0149±0.0003	799±17	695±34	1046.0±2.9
CNKS-3-113	11.3	694.5±1.6	2015±6	91.3±1.4	994.5±4.3	0.0161±0.0002	881±14	781±25	996.9±4.3
CNKS-3-140	14	803.1±0.9	2668±54	88.9±2.0	963.7±2.0	0.0179±0.0002	998±11	887±37	966.3±2.0
CNKS-3-168	16.8	656.3±1.0	4911±99	50.1±1.2	1033.4±3.2	0.0228±0.0003	1226±17	1057±77	1036.7±3.2
CNKS-3-192	19.2	628.7±1.1	2064±7	118.8±1.9	1052.7±3.2	0.0237±0.0004	1263±20	1158±30	1056.3±3.2
CNKS-7-36	3.6	149.7±0.4	32760±251	5.3±0.5	839.0±4.8	0.0702±0.0066	4238±403	2523±1079	845.2±5.4
CNKS-7-79	7.9	131.3±0.1	61230±1226	3.9±0.1	774.5±2.5	0.1106±0.0019	6984±124	3772±3580	782.9±8.3
CNKS-7-122	12.2	155.1±0.3	1040±4	188.3±2.9	784.6±4.9	0.0766±0.0011	4770±74	4603±91	795.0±5.0
CNKS-7-151	15.1	171.4±0.2	7132±143	34.4±0.9	779.3±2.3	0.0869±0.0013	5441±84	4700±487	789.9±2.6
CNKS-7-186	18.6	250.3±0.3	2702±54	140.8±3.0	834.3±2.2	0.0922±0.0008	5603±47	5371±129	847.2±2.3
CNKS-7-240	24	152.9±0.3	2084±9	124.4±3.0	832.0±5.7	0.1029±0.0025	6275±155	6002±188	846.3±5.9
CNKS-7-295	29.5	2701.4±12.0	24063±127	267.5±2.4	708.2±3.9	0.1443±0.0012	9583±88	9371±115	727.3±4.0
CNKS-7-340	34	1052.8±1.8	23682±475	379.5±7.6	423.7±2.2	0.5177±0.0012	4810±163	47598±352	484.7±2.5
CNKS-7-418	41.8	167.0±0.3	636±4	3372.1±26.4	559.2±4.7	0.7783±0.0035	71834±532	71710±533	684.8±5.8
CNKS-9-4	0.4	102.4±0.1	2703±54	4.3±0.6	849.4±2.8	0.0069±0.0010	406±57	-71±300	849.3±2.9
CNKS-9-26	2.6	147.5±0.3	12299±39	4.1±0.4	707.5±4.9	0.0206±0.0022	1325±145	-163±734	707.3±5.1
CNKS-9-73	7.3	218.0±0.7	14600±62	11.1±0.6	797.3±5.8	0.0448±0.0025	2753±156	1206±618	800.2±6.0
CNKS-9-116	11.6	171.7±0.2	7476±150	14.1±0.7	835.0±3.2	0.0371±0.0016	2226±98	1473±499	838.6±3.4
CNKS-9-179	17.9	154.2±0.5	20215±116	8.3±0.5	820.8±5.6	0.0660±0.0040	4021±249	1852±1093	825.3±6.2
CNKS-9-232	23.2	239.4±0.6	1623±68	16.9±0.8	741.4±5.6	0.0697±0.0033	4441±212	3250±608	748.4±5.8
CNKS-9-264	26.4	195.1±0.2	12681±254	20.5±0.5	771.4±2.6	0.0807±0.0008	5066±51	3937±757	780.2±3.1
CNKS-9-388	38.8	225.3±0.7	15664±73	19.0±0.5	796.6±5.6	0.0798±0.0022	4945±141	3757±583	805.3±5.8
CNKS-9-444	44.4	271.4±0.8	85000±915	8.6±0.5	773.3±5.1	0.1633±0.0086	10480±580	5205±2737	784.9±7.9
CNKS-9-584	58.4	2754.8±11.2	4281±15	5850.6±28.9	414.3±3.2	0.5507±0.0029	52442±384	52349±384	480.4±3.7
CNKS-9-664	66.4	104.1±0.2	3718±10	355.3±2.6	507.8±5.1	0.7696±0.0057	74250±834	73551±888	625.1±6.4

- 1110 *δ²³⁴U = ((²³⁴U/²³⁸U)_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1111 δ²³⁴U = ((²³⁴U/²³⁸U)_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1112 ²³⁴U = ((²³⁴U/²³⁸U)_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1113 ³⁴U = ((²³⁴U/²³⁸U)_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1114 ⁴U = ((²³⁴U/²³⁸U)_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1115 U = ((²³⁴U/²³⁸U)_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1116 = ((²³⁴U/²³⁸U)_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1117 = ((²³⁴U/²³⁸U)_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1118 ((²³⁴U/²³⁸U)_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1119 ((²³⁴U/²³⁸U)_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1120 [²³⁴U/²³⁸U]_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1121 [²³⁴U/²³⁸U]_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1122 ³⁴U/²³⁸U]_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1123 ⁴U/²³⁸U]_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1124 U/²³⁸U]_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1125 ²³⁸U]_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1126 ²³⁸U]_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} =
- 1127 ³⁸U]_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} = δ²³⁴U_{measured} ×
- 1128 ⁸U]_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} = δ²³⁴U_{measured} ×
- 1129 U]_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} = δ²³⁴U_{measured} ×
- 1130 U]_{activity} - 1) × 1000. ** δ²³⁴U_{initial} was calculated based on ²³⁰Th age (T), i.e., δ²³⁴U_{initial} = δ²³⁴U_{measured} ×

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Climate change has profound influence on the Central Asian environment, due to limited water resources. Recognizing the history and variability of past climate changes and understanding the dynamic processes are crucial to understanding the climate dynamics in this region and thus our ability to project its changes in the future. Two hypotheses have been proposed to explain the observed changes. One is that variations related to the westerlies dominated the climatic and environmental changes over Central Asia; the other suggests that monsoon-related moisture reached western China and led to a moister early and middle Holocene.

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